

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Determinants of career choice among secondary school students in Enugu east education zone

EGBO ANTHONIA CHINONYELUM, UZUAGU SAMUEL CHINWENDU * and EGBO CHINONYE EMMANUELLA

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu, Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(03), 1786–1795

Publication history: Received on 05 May 2024; revised on 18 June 2024; accepted on 21 June 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.3.1852>

Abstract

This study examined determinants of career choice among secondary school students in Enugu East Education Zone. The study specifically examined the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East, ascertained the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East, evaluated the extent peer groups influence the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East and also investigated the influence of the school environment on the choice of career among secondary school students. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Related literature was reviewed under the conceptual framework, theoretical studies, theoretical framework, related empirical studies, and summary. The study adopted a census survey research design. The study was conducted among secondary schools in Enugu education zone. The population for the study was 334 students. There was no sampling of the study because of the manageable size of the population. A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection and was designed to elicit appropriate information from the respondents. To ascertain the face validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was given to two experts in the Department of Educational Management and one expert from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education all from the Faculty of Education, ESUT. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was calculated using the Cronbach Alpha method. The results of the analysis indicated reliability indices of 0.85, 0.81, 0.76, 0.83, and 0.84 for clusters A, B, C, D, and E. The overall reliability index was 0.82 which made the instrument reliable. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings regarding the influence of parental factors on the choice of career between male and female students. Based on the findings, the study recommends among others that parental impositions regarding their children's choice of career often result in career failure. In realization of this, parents should guide their children through the decision-making process. Parents are advised to allow their wards free hands in their career choices that will relate to their interests, aptitude, passion, and ability.

Keywords: Career; Career Choice; Secondary School Students; Counsellors; Determinants

1. Introduction

Career choice has become a complex science with the advent of information technology, the emergency of post-industrial revolution, and job competition, and as such, education is universally recognized to be the answer to the socio-economic problems of the world. Nations and individuals look up to education to provide a clue or possibly, a cure for poverty, ignorance, joblessness, hunger, bad governance, poor communication system, and inadequate shelter among other things.

* Corresponding author: EGBO ANTHONIA CHINONYELUM

Adegboyega, (2017) opined that every nation of the world aspires towards quality of life and social status. Most students who are in secondary schools do not have adequate information about occupational opportunities to help them make appropriate career choices. This has led to so many swings in career paths after graduation from the university. Hence, this has highlighted career selection as one of many important choices students make in determining their plans, this decision will impart on them throughout their lives. Hence, it is important to figure out the factors or determinants of career choice among secondary school students, to see if one can help guide students to make the right and rational career choice. Thus, with the advent of information technology, the emergence of post-industrial revolutions, and job competition, the choice of career has become a complex science. These have given rise to scholars' interest in the factors influencing career choice not just among students alone, but among adults. The essence of who the student is will revolve around what the students want to do with their lifelong work. No matter one's age, the choice of career or desire is an important question for everybody.

A lot of students in secondary schools believe that their future is a glorious adventure in which they are bound to succeed (Salami and Salami, 2016). Many of them have the idea that they would be able to work in the public or private establishments as soon as they complete their secondary education. Student in secondary schools like many other young adult are always worried about what they will do with their lives, the kind of adult they will become, and so on. They are concerned about early entry into the occupational world and finding productive and rewarding places, fast changing societies where employment is unlikely to be available on a scale sufficient to absorb more than a small fraction of the young people when they do arrive at the labour market. How the young people of today meet the problem for tomorrow will depend upon the amount of success they make in planning for that tomorrow.

A career plays a very fundamental and significant role in the life of the individual not only because it determines the pattern of income but also because it affects the individual's personality and concepts in life. A career, therefore, is a choice pursuit, life work or success in one's profession occupied by a person throughout his/her lifetime. In a nutshell, a career is the totality of work one does in his/her lifetime and is person-centered, and is of utmost importance to every individual as he/she prepares for the future. A career can be defined as the sequence and variety of occupations undertaken for a significant period of a person's life and with opportunities for progress. More broadly, a 'career' includes life roles, leisure activities, learning and work. It includes the sum total of paid and unpaid work, learning and life roles you undertake throughout your life (Hammell, 2014; Adegboyega, 2017).

A career is a life pursuit, life work or success in one's profession occupied by a person throughout his or her lifetime. A career is the totality of work one does during a lifetime and as it is person centered, it is of utmost importance to every individual as he or she prepares for the future. Stebleton (2017) indicated that, a career is the totality of experience through which one learns about and prepares to engage in work as part of his way of living. A career is a lifelong process that is unique for every individual. There are many factors that contribute to an individual's career such as self-concept, interest, skill, knowledge, personality, ethnicity, age and gender. Choosing a career is something that is very hard to decide, especially as one's life will depend on it.

One's career may be in business, law, teaching, or entertainment professional way of life such that the former has implications for the makeup of the latter. A person may or may not "make money" or "earn a living" from a career, but a person who has a career may very well seem internally related to the work and way of life so that they become a part of his personal identity for practical purposes. A career usually imposes certain terms upon its pursuit. For example, it may require a certain specific location or type of location, a certain kind of geography or climate, a certain mix of uses of body and mind, or certain kinds of education and training. Such terms generally force some elements into and others out of a person's way of life. Careers may not dictate all the elements of one's way of life so that a career choice is the only serious life decision one makes; but careers certainly restrict and focus options in the many subparts of human lives, and it would be difficult to exaggerate the importance of career choice among the major decisions persons can make. Career choice and selection is one of many important choices students will make in determining their future plans and this decision will impact them throughout their lives (Borchert, 2012).

Career choice is something that is very hard to decide, especially as his/her life will depend on it. Stebleton (2017) indicated that a career is the totality of experience through which one learns about and prepares to engage in work as part of his way of living. Splete, Weaver and Atiyyah (2011) stressed that a career is an enjoyable process that occurs over the life span and includes homes, schools and community. Every human being needs to do one job or the other to help contribute his/her value to the development of the country. The world is marking such drastic demand upon the coming workers, every truthful man and woman, every teacher and reflecting parent is planning way to fit the students for the life and needs of this new century (Adegboyega, 2017).

Since the early 2000s, career development or vocational guidance as it was then known, has increasingly gained more and more attention and respect. In essence, career counselling is a specialty within the profession of counselling. It is one that fosters the vocational development and work adjustment of an individual's abilities, interests, and goals along with the work roles structured by the community and occupations organized by companies that assist individuals in deciding and making suitable and viable choices. Popoola (2014) refers to the need for one to discuss with one's peer school counsellors, parents, and teachers the choices regarding life span work as a "career convention" or a "career conference". A career convention according to Popoola is an instrument of career information. Work experience during industrial training or those experiences acquired during vocational education also aids the students in their choice of career. This is a technique in which students do jobs under realistic conditions without payment. This may help them choose a career for that effort.

Roach (2010) observed the influence that the home has on a child's learning is a fundamental concept of life. This cause and most of the habits and basic adjustments were established during pre-school years by highlighting the fact that home and parents occupy the most important position in a child's education. It should be stressed that work experience is not an attempt to find jobs for the students but an attempt to widen the horizons of students and ease the ultimate transition from school to work. This is usually based on the information given to the school by the parents. Such guidance and information are necessary because most school children are adolescents and are controlled by double standards, hypocrisy, truancy, materialism, and dishonesty.

Borchert (2012) observed that several factors influenced the career choices of high school students and identifying these factors would give parents, educators, and industry an idea as to where students place most of their trust in the career selection process. These factors include the students' immediate environment, opportunities available to the student, and finally his/her personality. He further observed that every student carries a unique history of their past and this determines how they view the world. In some cases, the career chosen is a result of a significant impact or impression made in the student's life, leading to a definite career choice.

Parents' educational background may influence student views on whether or not to continue their education. Someone they saw on television may have influenced the student, or parents may have demanded that they assume a family business.

These are various environmental factors that would lead a student to a chosen career. The environment in which a student is brought up may greatly influence the career that one chooses. The student's support system made up of parents, relatives, siblings, peers, teachers, and counsellors may be the most important environmental factor. Lawyers, Doctors, Teachers, Accountants, and Engineers, are some of the occupations which may run in families as children take up the careers of their parents. For example, students who have lived in a hospital environment may choose a career dealing with medicine. On the other hand, they may hate the hospital environment and consequently never choose a career that has anything to do with a hospital or medicine. Those who live near Airports may choose a career in piloting due to their fascination whenever they see airplanes flying over their homes (Natalie, 2016).

In some cases, the career chosen is as a result of a significant impact or impression made in the student's life, leading to a definite career choice. Parents' educational background may influence student views on whether or not to continue their education.

Career choice is one of the principal gridlocks that poses difficulties in any student's life. Many factors that are intricately knotted play out in this process (Kazi & Akhlaq, 2017). This implies that the process of career choice is not simple and involves a difficult process of decision-making. In our day, career choice does not only demand the development of calculated plans but also exhaustive career consultation to fiddle with the ever-budding socio-economic state of affairs. Nearly every one of the students in secondary schools lacks precise information about occupational opportunities to help them in navigating their career path thus, the anticipated life expectations marred (Ombaba, Keraro, Sindabi & Asienyo, 2014). The dearth of occupational information makes these students vulnerable to environmental influences.

The concept of environment means the surviving atmosphere of a life form that includes man (Puja, 2016). The author explains further that the environment and the life forms therein are two self-motivated and intricate constituents of the natural world. Regulation of the existence of man and other life forms is done by the environment. Man work together with the environment more energetically than other life existence. Typically, Puja (2016) submitted that the resources and atmospheric energy within man and other life forms denote the environment.

Contributing, Davis (2021) defined the environment as consisting of rudiments, factors, and circumstances in the background that exert consequences on the increase, development, achievement, or survival of man and other life forms

(Davis, 2021). The author stressed further that environment is the summation of physical, biological and cultural elements settings that may be favourable or unfavourable that surrounds us at a given point in time and space. Operationally, environment connotes the ambience of man and other life forms which influence their existence and maturity through stable undeviating contact.

Supporting Davis's aspect of the environment, Tope (2011) explained these aspects of the environment to represent the following- the natural environment to consist of man's background which relates to natural occurrences such as air, water, land, mountains, rivers cum average temperature. The organic/biological environment consisting of living things, flora and fauna including man. These life forms are mutually dependent and they depend on the natural milieu for continued existence with the prop up of the social environment.

Social environment connotes that which affects man's dealings and relationship patterns in the cause of his existence in the natural location (Tope, 2011). The author noted that the social milieu includes all the collective associations and bodies in the form of instructive, entertaining, religious, industrial, and profitable platforms created by man for its benefit. In addition, Tope (2011) opined that the inclusion of social agents such as the family, religion, education, peer group and even political group make the social setting functional. Owing to these inclusions by

Tope, the researchers find it apposite to bear out this study in light of Tope's (2011) concept of the social environment.

Social environmental factors include the family, the social environment, peers, societal values, the technological advancement of the society, and religious orientation among others (Akosah-twumasi, 2018). Hewitt (2010) admitted that virtually all students are inclined to the careers that their parents appreciate. Contributing, Nyarko-Sampson (2013) throws further light on the emotional demands that parents exert regarding careers selection. Parents make a selfdetermining enquiry regarding the career they think is most suitable for their children. Correspondingly, studies carried out in remote parts of Nigeria according to Oyamo and Amoth (2008), showed that students in the remote parts of the nation tend to solicit assistance from parents than students from developed areas.

More so, teachers exert less influence on the career choice of students than parents. Buttressing further, Ukwueze and Obiefuna (2017) noted that the socioeconomic status and educational background of parents influence the children's choice of career.

Students' choice of career is not independent of the society where they live. Fouad, Kim, Ghosh, Chang, and Figueiredo (2016) highlighted that students' career aspirations are regulated by the cultural practices and value orientation of society. Societal values and careers connote the way principles in a society affect an individual's choices and work activities. (Akosah-twumasi, et al. 2018). The principles and ethics of a given society influence careers in several ways (Hui & Lent, 2018). These authors opined that societal cherished standards and principles are the shared indoctrination that distinguishes one group from another in the mind. Since individuals are products of the societal value system, the type of jobs available, the job remuneration, and modes of operation that are valued are determined by these set of values. By implication, our perspectives of the importance of work and the type of work are being governed by the values in society. These governing principles not only shape the career and work decisions made by individuals, they equally provide yardsticks for policies made by organizations (Fouad, Kim, Ghosh, Chang, & Figueiredo, 2016).

In discussing the issue of factors influencing career choice, the student's gender cannot be overruled. This implies that the student's gender can make for relative differences in the influence of these environmental factors (Akosah-twumasi, 2018). This means the gender gap in career choice still exists. Gender is defined as roles, behaviours, activities socially constructed which defines the features that a particular society considers for men and women. In addition, Woolfolk (2010) defined gender as personality traits and manners a given society deems fitting for both sexes. Individuals of different sex in each society have work stereotypes in which they do not need to be engaged. The influences of these environmental factors are possibly regulated by the perceived gender bias. The study of Gokuladas (2010) on the factors of career choice of engineering students in India, perceptions of factors influencing career choice are diversely viewed by both genders. Correspondingly, Cheung, Wan, Fan, Leong, Mok (2013) reported that parents and teachers have more influence on girls than boys in terms of career choice. Durosaro and Nuhu (2012) established in their study that gender was a very significant factor in the career choice of senior secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis. Based on the studies reported so far, the researchers are motivated to explore factors influencing career choice of secondary school students in Enugu East.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Nigeria is rapidly developing her technological education, which has made the society more complex than it was in the past. The number of occupation has increased greatly and also there are many careers within one occupation. For instance, farming which was a simple occupation some years ago is now a very complex occupation within many careers to choose from.

These included poultry, farming vegetable farming, e.t.c the implication of this is specialization. This is why the family, peer group, school environment and even the larger society influence the decision any student might make in choosing a life career. This constitutes a problem as students often make wrong choice.

It has been noticed that many secondary school students are confronted with the problem of choosing a suitable career. This is evident in the reported poor academic performance, lack of interest in schooling and incessant dropout in their academic pursuit among others. The paucity of career information by such social settings of the student's upbringing is expected to facilitate the student's conscientious career decision needed for survival in the world. Consequently, students are bereft of alternatives to career choices that are not consistent with their inherent capacities and invariably turn to uninformed channels, like their friends, family, to make the very important decision of choosing suitable career paths. This leads to a large number of students falling into careers by happenstance instead of via an objective and holistic analysis to find a fit that takes all aspects of their personality and skills into consideration.

Many adults complain of a high level of frustration and stress with their careers. These issues are quite significant among secondary school students in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State. Thus, the researchers seek to explore the factors influencing career choice of secondary school students in Enugu East.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose was to determine the factors influencing career choice of secondary school students in Enugu East. Specifically this study sought to:

- Identify the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East.
- Ascertain the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- What is the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East?
- What are the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East?

1.4. Hypotheses

The following Null (Ho) hypotheses were developed to guide the study;

- H01: there is no significant difference in mean scores between male and female students regarding the influence of parental factors on their choice of career.
- H02: there is no significant difference in mean scores of male and female students regarding the influence of societal culture on their choice of career.

2. Research method

2.1. Research Design

The researcher adopted a census survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015), a census survey research design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data or information from every member of the population. This design is suitable for this study because it involved the collection of data from all the participants.

This study was carried out in all the secondary schools in Enugu East Education zone, Enugu East is a Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. Enugu East is made up 3 zones/districts Nike-Uno, Ugwogo and Mbuli NjodoIts, headquarters are in the town of Nkwo Nike. Enugu East Local Government Area is one of the lower tier administrations within Enugu state and it is under the Enugu west senatorial zone. This local government operates within the Enugu state government to provide ⁸² development to the communities surrounding them.

The population of the study is made up of secondary school students in Enugu-North, Enugu-East and Isi-uzo, the population for the study was 334 students which comprised of 222 male and 112 female students. Also, there are 98 students in urban schools and 236 rural schools (Source: Statistics Unit of PPSMB, 2021).

The researcher used the 334 students who formed the population for the study because it was manageable in size. This is in line with Uzoagulu (2011) who posited that, if the population for a study is in hundreds, the researcher can make use of the whole respondents in the study.

The instrument for data collection was the researchers' developed questionnaire titled: "Students' Perception of career Choice of Students Questionnaire (PCCSQ)". The instrument was made up of two sections: A and B. Section A is on the background information of the respondents while section B contains items on students' perception of career choice of students. Section B of the instrument is divided into four clusters based on the number of research questions. Cluster 1 has 10 items on parental factors, cluster 2 has 7 items on choice of career. The researcher made use of a 4-point rating scale structured of Very Great Extent (VGE) = 4 points, Great Extent (GE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point for the instrument.

The instrument was faced validated by three experts. Two were from Department of Educational Management and one was from Measurement and Evaluation unit in the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education all from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology. The researcher presented copies of the purposes, research questions as well as the hypotheses to the experts.. The observations and corrections of the experts guided the production of the final draft that was used for the study.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, 40 copies of the instrument (PCCSQ) were given to 24 male and 16 female students in public secondary schools in EnuguNorth, Enugu-East and Isi-uzo. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, the Cronbach Alpha method was used to compute the internal consistency of the instrument. The choice of Cronbach Alpha for computing the reliability was because the answer to the items were designed. The computation yielded 0.80 for cluster 1, 0.78 for cluster 2, the instrument had an overall reliability index of 0.80 which was used for data collection.

The 334 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents by the researcher with the help of two research assistants.

The data were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The degrees of great extent and low extent were determined by finding the mean of the values assigned to the options. In rating the computed mean scores, means of 2.50 and above was regarded as being great extent while the means below 2.50 was regarded as low extent. The criterion mean of 2.50 was determine by summing up the weighted options (4+3+2+1=10) and dividing it by total number of response options (4) as follows; $10/4=2.50$.

The decision rule for the hypotheses was, hypothesis would not be rejected when the t-calculated value is less than the critical table value, but rejected when the t-calculated value is greater than the critical table value.

3. Result

The researcher in this chapter presents the data collected from respondents as well as the results of their analysis. The presentation and analysis are done according to the research questions and hypotheses. The summary of findings from the analysis is also presented.

3.1. Research Question 1: What is the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East?

In Enugu East. The mean scores of male students ranged from 2.50 to 2.65 while that of female students ranged from 2.52 to 2.65. In addition, they had cluster means of 2.57 and 2.58 and standard deviations of 0.94 and 0.92 respectively.

The SD of the respondents are small, showing that the respondents' mean scores are closely clustered around the mean. Thus, parental factors influences the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East to a great extent.

Table 1 Mean response scores of male and female students on the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East N= 299

ITEMS	Male = 206		Female = 93	
	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
Societal culture affects the career choice of students when;				
My parents have control over my choice of career	2.56	0.99	2.59	0.90
The career of my parents is what I will like to choose...	2.58	0.91	2.55	0.91
I choose the career my parents favour	2.59	0.98	2.55	0.95
My parents' educational attainment affects my choice of career	2.65	0.95	2.63	0.91
I do not like the career chosen for me by my parents	2.55	0.90	2.58	0.80
My parents' socio-economic background determines my choice of career	2.54	0.95	2.52	1.00
Other family members have the greatest control over my career choice	2.55	0.91	2.60	0.91
I only need my parents' advice to make my career choice	2.61	0.90	2.65	0.93
Parents plays significant role in selection career chice for students	2.50	0.99	2.59	0.90
My parents are involved in critical decision making by the students.	2.52	0.88	2.55	0.95
Cluster Mean/SD	2.57	0.94	2.58	0.92

Data presented on Table 1 show the analysis of male and female students on the influence of parental factors on the choice of career among secondary school students

3.2. Research Question 2: What are the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East?

Table 2 Mean response scores of male and female students on the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East N= 299

S/N	ITEMS	Male = 206		Female = 93	
		X	SD	x	SD
11	My societal culture is open to all career choices available	2.59	0.86	2.61	0.92
12	I should make a career choice that favours my societal culture	2.62	0.88	2.60	0.95
13	I was unable to make other career choices because of the societal culture	2.57	0.89	2.53	0.95
14	Societal ratings of different careers determine my choice of career	2.55	0.93	2.52	0.88
15	The height of development in society influenced my choice of career	2.52	0.95	2.54	0.99
16	Society's level of technological advancement contributed to my career choice	2.63	0.91	2.56	1.00
17	Social cultural critically influence the career choice of secondary school studentsn Enugu East LGA	2.58	0.90	2.56	0.95
Cluster Mean/SD		2.58	0.90	2.56	0.95

Data presented on Table 2 show the analysis of male and female students on the influence of societal culture on the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East. The mean scores of male students ranged from 2.52 to 2.63 while that of female students ranged from 2.52 to 2.61. In addition, they had cluster means of 2.58 and 2.56 and standard deviations of 0.90 and 0.95 respectively. The SD are small signifying that the respondents' responses are

similar. This implies that societal culture influences the choice of career among secondary school students in Enugu East to a great extent.

3.3. Hypotheses

3.3.1. **Ho₁**: there is no significant difference in mean ratings regarding the influence of parental factors on the choice of career between male and female students.

Table 3 t-test of significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students on mean ratings regarding the influence of parental factors on the choice of career between male and female students

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Students	206	2.57	0.94				
Female Students	93	2.58	0.92	297	0.09	1.96	Ho not Rejected

Table 6 shows that t-cal of 0.09 is less than the t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 297 degree of freedom. This means that there is no significant difference in mean ratings regarding the influence of parental factors on the choice of career between male and female students. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

3.3.2. **Ho₂**: there is no significant difference in mean ratings regarding the influence of societal culture on the choice of career between male and female students.

Table 4 t-test of significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students on the extent to which students perceive that societal culture affects choice of career between male and female students Group

	n	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Students	206	2.58	0.90				
Female Students	93	2.56	0.95	297	0.17	1.96	Ho not Rejected

Table 7 shows that t-cal of 0.17 is less than the t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 297 degree of freedom. This signifies that there is no significant difference in mean ratings regarding the influence of societal culture on the choice of career between male and female students. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

4. Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the responses of the students and the analysis presented indicate that there is a significant influence of social factors on career choice among secondary school students which has implications for school library development. Truly, the issue of career choice factors is a multifaceted phenomenon that requires an understanding of teachers, parents and school administrators and all the stakeholders. More so, the findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the influence of the social- environmental factors among secondary school students in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

- Parental impositions regarding their children's choice of career often result in career failure. In realization of this, parents should guide their children through the decision making process. Parents are advised to allow their wards free hands in their career choices that will relate to their interest, aptitude, passion and ability.
- The federal ministry of education should award scholarships to students to help those from a low socio-economic background to pursue their career aspirations without being frustrated by finance.
- Societies at large should discourage all forms of ratings, and recognition of some careers as it brings stereotypes but rather efforts should be made to recognize and publicize the relevance of all careers to societal development.

- Curriculum planners should include career information in their curriculum design such that will enable students to identify careers and its prospects so that students will not make a poor career choice. More so school library development should be encouraged.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Adegboyega, L. O. (2017). Environmental influence on career choice of undergraduates at University of Ilorin: Implications for counselling. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2), 59-70.
- [2] Akosah-twumasi, P., Emeto, T. I., Lindsay, D., Tsey, K. & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2018). A systematic review of Factors that influence youths career choices- the role of culture. *Front. Educ.* Vol. 3, 58.
- [3] Akosah-twumasi, Y., Emeto, G., Lindsay, J., Tsey, O. & Malau-Aduli, I. (2018).
- [4] Transforming careers from linear to multidirectional career paths: Organizational and individual perspectives. *Career Development International*, 9(1), 58- 73.
- [5] Borchert M (2012). *Career choice factors of high school students*. (Master's Thesis, Unpublished). Stout, Menomonie, University of Wisconsin.
- [6] Borchert, M. (2012). Career choice factors of high school students. *The Graduate School University of Wisconsin-Stout Menomonie*. WI 54751
- [7] Cheung, F. M., Wan, S. L. Y., Fan, W., Leong, F., & Mok, P. C. H. (2013). Collective contributions to career efficacy in adolescents: across-cultural study. *J. Vocat. Behav.* 83, 237-244. doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2013.05.004
- [8] Davis, C. P. (2021). Medical definition of environment. Retrieved from, <https://www.medicinenet.com/environment/definition.htm>
- [9] Durosaro, I., & Nuhu, M. A. (2012). Gender as a Factor in the Career Choice Readiness of Senior Secondary School Students in Ilorin Metropolis of Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(14), 109 - 113.
- [10] Fouad, N. A. & Byars, A. M. (2004). "Work: Cultural Perspectives on Career Choices and Decision-making. In Carter. R. T. (ed.) in *Handbook of Racialcultural Psychology and Counseling. 1, Theory and Research*, by New York: Wiley. Pp. 232-255.
- [11] Fouad, N. A., Kim, S. Y., Ghosh, A., Chang, W., & Figueiredo, C. (2016). Family influence on career decision making: Validation in India and the United States. *J. Career Assess.* 24, 197-212.
- [12] Hammell, K. W. (2014). Dimensions of meaning in the occupations of daily life. *Canadian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 5, 296-305.
- [13] Hewitt, J. (2010). Factors influencing career choice. Cited from www.ehow.com on 15/02/2020. <http://search.eb.com/search?query=environment&x=10&y=9>.
- [14] Hui, K., & Lent, R. W. (2018). The roles of family, culture and social cognitive variables in the career interest and goals of Asian American college students, *J. Couns. Psychol.* 65, 98-109. Doi: 10.1037/cou0000235
- [15] Kazi, A. S. & Akhlaq, A. (2017). Factors Affecting Student's Career Choice. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, Vol., No.2, pp187-196 <http://www.ue.edu.pk/jrre>
- [16] Mugenda, O. M. & Mugenda, A. G. (2019). Research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. *Nairobi: African Centre for Technology Studies Press*.

- [17] Natalie. M.F. (2016). Factors influencing career choice of adolescents and young adults in rival Pennsylvania. *Journal of Extension*, 44(3),239-250.
- [18] Nworgu, B. G. (2006). *Educational Research: Basic Issues & Methodology*. Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- [19] Nyarko-Sampson, E. (2013). Tutors' participation in guidance and counselling programmes in Colleges of Education in northern Ghana. *Ife Psychologia: An International Journal*, 21, (2), 141-149.
- [20] Ombaba, S., Keraro, F. N., Sindabi, A. M. & Asienyo, B. O. (2014). Adequacy of Career Guidance Resources in Secondary Schools in Nakuru, Kisii and Migori Counties, Kenya. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Sciences*. Vol.6(4), 921-928.
- [21] Onayase, D., and Onayase, A. (2009). "The Relationship between Personality types and Career Choice of Secondary School Students in Federal Government Colleges in Nigeria". *Anthropologist* 11(2).
- [22] Oyamo, O. R., & Amoth, D (2008). Choice of final year options by undergraduate students at the Moi School of Information Sciences. *East African Journal of Information Science*.
- [23] Popoola, S.O (2014). Career and other factors influencing post – secondary Decisions; Survey of High School Students in Alberta, Canada. *The high School Journal*, 12, 267-275.
- [24] Puja, M. (2016). *Meaning, Definition and Components of Environment: yourArticleLibrary.com*.
- [25] Roach, K. L. (2010). The role of perceived parental influences on the career selfefficacy of college students. *Counsellor Education Master's Theses. Paper 88*. Retrieved from http://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1087&context=edc_the_ses
- [26] Salami O. O and Salami, O. O. (2016).The Factors Determining the Choice of Career Among Secondary School Students.The International Journal of Engineering and Science (IJES) 2(6):33-44
- [27] Salami, S.O. (1999).Relationship between Work Values and Vocational Interests among High SchoolStudents in Ibadan.Mgeria African Journal of Educational Research5 (2): 65-74
- [28] Splete, H. H., Weaver Paquette, E., & Atiyyah, S. S. (2011). A view of global career development and practitioner training. *Career Planning and Adult Development Journal*, 27, 87-94. Stebleton, M. J. (2017). Career counselling with African immigrant colleges: theoretical approaches and implications for practice. *Career Development Quarterly*, 55(4), 290- 312.
- [29] Taylor, J., Harris, M. and Taylor, S. (2004). "Parents have their say about their college aged children's career decisions". *National Association of Collegians Employers Journal*, 64 (3).
- [30] Tope, O. (2011). *The influence of peer group on adolescent's academic performance: A case study of some selected schools in Ogun State, Nigeria*: Egobooster Books.
- [31] Ukwueze, A. C. & Obiefuna, C. C. (2017). Influence of Selected Environmental Factors on Career Choice of Secondary School Students in Lagos Metropolis of Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Empirical Studies in Psychology and Education*, 19(1), 101-116.